

Mobile Edge Computing

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Abstract—Latest generation mobile networks aim to use multi-tier heterogeneous cellular networks integrated with cloud computing to provide users with low latency and energy-aware service. However, for high bandwidth and low latency services, edge/fog computing comes into the scenario. In edge/fog computing, the intermediate devices between end users and cloud participate in processing and storage of data as well as execution of applications. Mobile edge computing provides cloud computing services at the edge of mobile network, which facilitates the developers, service providers as well as the users. Internet of Things (IoT) has become a principal component to design smart technological solutions for our daily life. For low latency and high bandwidth services, edge computing assisted IoT has become the pillar for the development of smart home, smart health etc. This chapter will discuss the overview of mobile edge computing along with its real time applications.

Keywords—Mobile edge computing, RAN, Cloud Computing, Cloud, IoT.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-Access Edge Computing which is formerly known as Mobile edge computing (MEC) [1] provides the cloud computing services at the edge of mobile network, which facilitates the developers, service providers as well as the users. In MEC the operators can open their Radio Access Network[1] edge to the authorized third parties in order to provide rapid and flexible deployment of interactive services and applications for the users. Computations are performed usually at the local network edge in edge computing instead of putting it to the remote cloud, that in turn reduces the latency. The network providers meet the customers' demand of good coverage and high bandwidth through the help of MEC. MEC enables Information Technology (IT) and Cloud Computing[2] facilities at the edge of the network.

The objective of MEC is to minimize the congestion, reduce latency, and provides better Quality of Service (QoS) by accomplishing the related processing tasks closer to the end user. MEC can be implemented as cellular base stations which in turn can offer rapid application deployment. We can define MEC as: MEC is a new network paradigm that provides information technology services and cloud computing capabilities within the mobile access network of mobile users and has become a technology.

MEC is a principle component for fifth generation (5G) network.

II. ARCHITECTURE OF MOBILE EDGE COMPUTING

Mobile edge computing architecture contains the following components:

- Mobile device
- Base station
- Cloudlet (in case of Wi-Fi)
- Edge Server
- Core network
- Cloud Maintaining the Integrity of the Specifications

Fig. 1. Architecture of Mobile Edge Computing

In case of cellular network cellular base station is used along with an edge server. In case of Wi-Fi i.e. Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) or Wireless Metropolitan Area Network (WMAN), cloudlet is used. As cloudlet itself offers the storage and computation facilities, it can act as edge server. The MEC architecture is presented in Fig.1. As observed from the figure, the mobile devices are connected with the base station (cellular network) or cloudlet (WMAN/WLAN). The base station is connected with edge server. The edge server is connected with the cloud through the core network. The mobile device users or mobile users and edge server are the key components of MEC, on basis of which two categories of services come [4]:

- Mobile user oriented service
- Edge server oriented service

For the first category, mobile users request for offloading data and/or computation. For the second category, resource management is crucial. Mobile user oriented service mainly deal with offloading. Offloading is of two types [4]:

- Data offloading: User requests for storing data.
- Computation offloading: User requests for execution of a computation.

III. APPLICATIONS OF MOBILE EDGE COMPUTING

There are several applications of MEC discussed as follows.

- MEC in IoT: IoT is an emerging research field nowadays. Use of MEC in IoT can enhance the QoS by bringing computation resources nearby the network edges [4]. It will offer scalable IoT framework for time critical applications. In IoT-MEC, the data collected using IoT devices get partially processed inside the edge devices, which makes the system faster, energy-efficient and reduces the network operation cost. A mobile edge IoT framework has been proposed in, where computing and storage resources are pushed nearby the IoT devices. Another approach Edge IoT has been proposed in where the data streams has been identified at the mobile edge.

- MEC in video streaming: To improve the Quality of Experience (QoE)[5] of video streaming in smart cities a method has been proposed in where users mobility pattern have been followed and “Follow Me Edge” concept has been implemented. This method reduces the network traffic as well as the delay.

- MEC in computation offloading: The convergence of cloud computing and mobile computing depends on high bandwidth edge to edge network. Edge and fog device based computation offloading. The use of edge and fog computing has reduced the delay and power consumption with respect to the cloud based system.

- MEC in UAV: The use of UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) can strengthen the coverage of relay services for the mobile users in limited infrastructure wireless systems [4]. Based on UAV a MCC[7] framework has been considered in where the mobile UAVs have computing ability to offer computation offloading facilities to the mobile users. This in turn reduces energy consumption meeting the QoS requirements. Here, offloading has been done through uplink and downlink communications between the UAV and the mobile users. This has solved the problem of joint optimization of the bit allocation in uplink and downlink communications. An edge computing based RAN framework has been proposed in, where the fronthaul and backhaul links are mounted on the UAVs, which provides faster response time and flexible deployment.

- MEC in smart healthcare: In smart health care health sensor devices capture the health status, and the sensor data are stored and processed inside the cloud servers. After processing the data, the health status of the user can be detected. In the use of fog computing for health care has been discussed. In the use of edge/fog framework in time-critical applications has been shown, where health care has been considered as a case study. By bringing the processing facility closer to the network edge, the delay which is a vital parameter for health care, can be reduced.

- MEC in smart home: In the use of fog computing in smart home has been demonstrated. By bringing the computing and storage resources nearby the network edge, the delay, jitter, and energy consumption of the user device can be reduced.

- MEC in retail: In a retail application has been discussed based on edge computing, which reduces the delay and energy consumption

IV. CHALLENGES IN MOBILE EDGE COMPUTING

Though the use of MEC has provided various advantages like low latency, low power consumption etc., still several challenges remain. The selection of edge device to meet different service requirements of multiple mobile users is a key factor, for which novel strategy is required. Moreover, edge devices have limited resources. Therefore, low-complexity edge device placement and scheduling become vital when large numbers of mobile users are present. Furthermore, the request of mobile user variable, therefore dynamic strategy is required which will deal with user requirements. Instead of these challenges, there are several other issues discussed as follows.

- Security: A edge based storage framework to deal with cyber threat. As a large number of mobile users are present, then privacy is another important issue. Here, the assessment of each mobile node is also very important along with the assessment of invulnerability. In intrusion detection system has been discussed based on decision tree. A pre-processing algorithm has been designed to digitize strings in a given dataset and after that the whole data is normalized. Then a decision tree based scheme has been used for the intrusion detection system.

- Resource management: Resource allocation and management is another major factor in MEC. Though several schemes have been proposed for deployment of cloudlets for optimal service provisioning, still resource management is a vital challenge in MEC. As multiple users are present and their requirements are also different and most importantly the users have mobility, the resource allocation, release, VM migration, delivery of required service with minimal latency are key challenges.

- Energy consumption: In few existing works has been shown that the use of edge based framework has reduced the power consumption of the user device. However, the energy consumption of the overall paradigm is also crucial. . Another

factor is decision making regarding offloading to edge/ fog or cloud; whether partial offloading will be done or multi-level full offloading will be done that is also important to reduce the total energy consumption of the paradigm.

- **Mobility based service provisioning:** The service provisioning becomes a challenge when the customer is mobile. Here the devices have mobility and frequently change their locations in many cases. In such a scenario, tracking the mobility of the user is very important to deliver the required service. The use of artificial intelligence can play a vital role in this case. Several approaches on trajectory analysis exist. The integration of these methods with service provisioning can open a new era in MEC.

- **User allocation based edge-cloud placement:** In order to improve the service quality and reduce the cost simultaneously, edge-cloud placement is an important factor. To deal with this challenge, user location can be considered and based on the location mobile users can be allocated to the edge-clouds. This can be treated as a multi objective optimization problem where the aim is load balancing and reduce the communication delay of the users.

- **Edge-based smart wearable system for maintenance in communication network:** The shortcomings of existing communication system are shortage of real time operation and data interaction maintenance. The decision making and execution process might suffer from inconvenient information interaction and shortage of field links. Use of edge computing can provide a smart wearable maintenance system for communication network. An edge computing based IoT platform can provide real time guidance that can help to enhance the efficacy and quality of on-site maintenance. Not only the issues discussed above, there are other challenges also like billing, simulation tool designing etc. For cloud computing simulation tools are already available in MATLAB, Python etc. Cloudsim [6] is a popular simulator for cloud computing. Edge Cloudsim has been built on Cloudsim to provide necessary functionalities for edge computing. For fog computing, iFogSim[6] simulator is present. Resource allocation in fog computing considering user mobility has been studied in where MyiFogSim[6] has been built as an extension of iFogSim. To effectively promote MEC development and standardization of experimental design, a simulator is required that will provide the computation, storage and networking facilities at the edge to the mobile users.

Another factor is decision making regarding offloading to edge/ fog or cloud; whether partial offloading will be done or multi-level full offloading will be done that is also important to reduce the total energy consumption of the paradigm.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper discussed architecture and working model of mobile edge computing. The use of edge computing provides lower latency and power consumption of the user device with respect to the cloud only system in case of computation offloading, which we have shown in theoretical and experimental results. The applications and challenges of mobile edge computing are also discussed.

VI. REFERENCES

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